

GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP AND THE PROMOTION OF GLOBAL SKILLS

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Suiane Costa Alves

PhD student in Education at the University of Vale do Rio dos Sinos. Member of the Center for International Studies in Education (CEIE) Research Group. Regional Coordinator of the Class Director Teacher Program SEDUC/CREDE 1. Email: suiane.alves@crede01.seduc.ce.gov.br

Marian Pereira da Costa

Master in Computing Applied to Educational Informatics at the State University of Ceará (UECE). Technician from the Regional Education Development Coordination (CREDE 1). Email: marian.cavalcante@crede01.seduc.ce.gov.br;

Ana Geovanda Mourão Cavalcante

Master in Management and Evaluation of Public Education from the Federal University of Juiz de Fora. Coordinator of the Regional Education Development Coordination SEDUC/CREDE 1. Email: geovanda@crede01.seduc.ce.gov.br

ABSTRACT

The present work aims to reflect on Global Citizenship and the role of the Class Director Teacher (PDT) in promoting global skills. The theoretical assumptions adopted were Alves (2022), UNESCO (2016), Ceará (2010), Lima (2017) Schwanke and Santos (2017), Winck et al. (2016). Methodologically, we developed bibliographical research, searching the main databases and digital repositories to support the proposed reflections. Finally, based on the results, we found how important the PDT's role is in citizenship training and the development of global skills. In this regard, the formation of global leaders permeates the school space as it contributes to empowerment, encouraging student protagonism not only in the school environment, but also in different spaces of citizenship.

Keywords: Global Citizenship. Class Director Professor. Global Skills.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the United Nations (UN, 1948), citizenship is an inherent right for every human being, guaranteeing access to housing, security and education. Given the current global scenario, the expansion of the definition of citizenship has become evident, characterized by global and interconnected relationships. In this sense, when we reflect on Global Citizenship and the role of the Class Director Teacher (PDT) in promoting global competencies, we are invited to transcend the challenges emerging from the classroom, motivating the student to integrate diverse perspectives, including the intellectual and socio-emotional, reverberating in the school academic environment and in the community in which it is inserted, contributing to the formation of global leaders through the empowerment of their capabilities and adaptation to different realities.

Studies on the diversity and complexity of the educational space have led educators and researchers to think of these spaces as opportunities for integrating cultures, being considered a strategic resource in promoting global skills. The understanding of global citizenship as the main driver of social transformations makes schools a space of opportunities and the construction of a new reality, guaranteeing peace through intellectual cooperation between nations, following global development and helping Member States in the search of solutions to the problems that challenge our society (UNESCO, 2016).

In this sense, this research is guided by the methodology of socio-emotional dialogues (INSTITUTO AYRTON SENNA, 2017), seeking the development and monitoring of skills in this area, which are based on dialogical practices, giving us support for the proposed reflections and making us reflect on the importance of the work carried out in promoting education for the formation of global skills.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This work was built from a literature review using the descriptors: 1) Global Citizenship; 2) Class Director Teacher; 3) Citizenship Training, standardized according to the *Institute of Education Sciences* (ERIC) arranged as follows: “Global citizenship” AND “Teacher Class Director” AND “Citizenship training”, using Boolean Operator strategies. The Spanish descriptors “Cuidadania Global” AND “Profesor Director de Clase” AND “Formación Ciudadana” were also used in the searches.

That said, a survey was carried out in the main databases and digital repositories in order to support the proposed reflections. Among the databases and digital repositories, we can mention: Journal Portal Brazilian Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD), Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES), Latin American Council of Social Sciences (CLACSO), Network of Researchers and Managers in the Internationalization of Higher Education in Latin America (REDALINT). The following results were found from the database, presented in sequence: Articles (5), Book chapter (1), Dissertations (2), Working document (4), Book (8), Theses (3) (Figure 1).

Among the databases researched, only one work related to the three descriptors used (and related to the research proposal), was found, which is the doctoral thesis entitled *Professor class director: a study between Brazil and Portugal about a policy educational project in the state of Ceará* , by author Vagna Brito de Lima, defended at the Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB) in 2017.

Figure 1: Survey of academic works linked to the main themes of this research in databases and digital repositories.

Source: Direct research (2022).

In this sense, based on the descriptors used, we noticed a scarcity of works that directly address Global Citizenship, Class Director Teacher and Citizen Training, giving us support for the proposed reflections. Next, it is possible to view the survey of scientific production by country (Table 1) (Figure 2).

Table 1: Survey of scientific production in absolute number by country

Country	Number of works
Brazil	09
Peru	09
Mexico	03
Argentina	01

1. Source: Prepared by the authors (2023).

Figure 2: Survey of scientific production in absolute numbers by country

2. Source: Prepared by the authors (2023).

3. GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP AND ITS MULTIPLE ASPECTS

Currently, one of the themes with great repercussion and debate among educators is global citizenship. The word citizenship emerged in Ancient Greece and was used by different societies over the centuries with varying meanings (POZIOMYCK; GUILHERME, 2022), having been used to determine the rights relating to individuals in a given location. The use of the word citizenship reverberates in reflections on the full exercise of civil and political rights, having been incorporated into the educational curriculum, acting as a tool for social transformation.

Legal documents that guide global education bring citizenship as one of the pillars of citizenship training, focusing on aspects such as intellectual autonomy, student protagonism, ethical-scientific production, as well as preparation for the world of work (UNESCO, 2016), composing one of the basic requirements of Curriculum Internationalization. Thus, education

for citizenship becomes part of the debate of governments, academic centers and education departments, strengthening the rule of law and democratic participation.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights guarantees the fundamental rights of the human being, such as the dignity and value of the human person, the equal rights of men and women and which decided to promote social progress and better living conditions (UN, 1948). From this perspective, the concept of citizenship seems to integrate the central notions of politics, linking itself to the idea of individual rights and belonging to a community, where the educational process integrates substantive functions in a global, intercultural, comparative and interdisciplinary dimension, fostering students' understanding of global issues.

In these terms, the concept of citizenship gained broad meaning when reflected in the conception of citizen training to act globally. The potential issue that mobilizes this dialogue is precisely the ever-increasing dimension of globalization and its effects on education and, more specifically, on learning. Curricula that demand global knowledge to meet the needs of the primary, secondary and tertiary sectors, and that end up impacting educational centers. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization , global citizenship encompasses the development of civil, political and social rights, guaranteeing human rights in all their breadth, promoting quality education (UNESCO, 2016).

The Incheon declaration presented the objectives of Education for 2030, which aim to ensure equitable education with inclusion, promoting lifelong learning opportunities and, in this sense, act as a foundation for transformative education (UNESCO, 2017). In view of this, thinking about global citizenship for the structuring of contemporary education invites us to reflect on three fundamental factors that can contribute to this process, mentioned below: 1) Professional qualifications of educators; 2) Lifelong learning; 3) Innovation and use of digital technologies in teaching.

For Bauman (2001, p. 25), "individualization seems to be the corrosion and slow disintegration of citizenship." The author (2001) is emphatic in stating that in the globalized world in which we live, human relationships are increasingly perishable, impacting the educational system and educational practice. Values such as respect, dignity, honesty are being replaced by consumption that is linked to purchasing power and the capitalist world. In this regard, we need to prioritize the provision of education for citizenship development, where the feeling of community occurs through the student's belonging and care for family and society. Within the global agendas in the field of education we have the development of automation and technological progress, where children and young people are immersed in global skills.

The European Commission Meeting that took place in Gothenburg, Sweden, discussed education and culture being key points for the future (EUROPEAN COMMISSION, 2017), constituting a foundation for global citizenship, contributing to the integral development of the student, allowing them to articulate knowledge and practices in an interdisciplinary way to promote common values, whose action will focus on promoting world peace.

4. TEACHER DIRECTOR PROGRAM AND CITIZENSHIP TRAINING

The Class Director Teacher (PDT) appears in Europe, more precisely in Portugal, as a successful experience of educational monitoring in its cognitive and socio-emotional aspects. The creation of DT in Portuguese schools in 1968 is part of the context of the emergence of Portuguese education, which sought to expand its education system, combining education with the political situation of the time (LIMA, 2017). Thus, the DT teacher acts as a tutor offering students differentiated support, enabling a closer relationship between school and family.

The Class Director is a teacher who teaches a subject in his/her area of training and simultaneously teaches the subject of Citizenship Training. Its duties are in line with the coordination between parents, management group, teachers and students, who make up the class[...] Problems of a personal or social, cultural, ethical, linguistic, cognitive and integration nature are discussed. The purpose of the actions is to promote values intrinsic to learning through supportive and social coexistence, where the actors are also spectators (LEITE; CHAVES, 2010, p.3).

Studies based on socio-emotional assessments show that students who have greater monitoring have better cognitive and emotional development conditions, preparing them to make choices. The PDT arrived in Brazil in 2007, having been exposed at the XVIII Meeting of the National Association of Education Policy and Administration (ANPAE) – Ceará Section, in 2007, where the Portuguese experience and the application of the pilot project were presented. in 2008 in the municipalities of Eusébio, Madalena and Canindé (CEARÁ, 2010). Regulated by Ordinance no. 1451/2017-SEDUC/GAB which provides for the capacity of the PDT and its duties, teaching classes in the common base subjects and training itineraries concomitantly with monitoring through Training for Citizenship and Development of Socio-Emotional Skills (FCDCSE) classes and assistance to students and their families (ALVES, *et. al.* . 2022).

The Ayrton Senna Institute is responsible for preparing the teaching material together with the Department of Education of the State of Ceará (SEDUC), being in dialogue with the areas of knowledge, becoming effective in view of the feasibility of the pedagogical action. In

this sense, citizenship training is supported by the FCDCSE curricular component, which aims to encourage students to become responsible, critical, active and intervening citizens, allowing them to work on their experiences on a personal and collective level (CEARÁ, 2015).

4.1. GLOBAL CITIZEN TRAINING

The United Nations (UN) together with the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) has been working from the perspective of Education for Global Citizenship (ECG), whose objective is to allow students of any age become active subjects, in your region and globally, in building more peaceful, tolerant, inclusive and safer societies.

In this context, ECG seeks to encourage respect for diversity and solidarity among students, with the aim of fostering a sense of humanity and belonging, comprising three basic conceptual dimensions, observed below: 1) Cognitive dimension; 2) Socio-emotional dimension; 3) Behavioral dimension (UNESCO, 2016).

Education for global citizenship is based on three conceptual dimensions or learning areas, namely: cognitive area, in which knowledge and reflection skills necessary to better understand the world and its complexities are worked on; socio-emotional area, which develops values, attitudes and social skills that allow students to live with others in a respectful and peaceful way; and behavioral area, which works on behavior, performance, practical application and student engagement (SCHWANKE; SANTOS, 2017, p.4)

In the FCDCSE curricular component classes, the 5 socio-emotional macro-competences are worked on (openness to new things, self-management, engagement with others, kindness and emotional resilience) and from these, 17 skills are identified, presented in the sequence: determination, focus , organization, persistence, responsibility, empathy, respect, confidence, stress tolerance, self-confidence, frustration tolerance, social initiative, assertiveness, enthusiasm, curiosity to learn, creative imagination and artistic interest (INSTITUTO AYRTON SENNA, 2017), aligned with the capabilities predicted by the three dimensions mentioned in the ECG.

Socio-emotional skills include a set of skills that each person has to deal with their own emotions, relate to others and manage life goals, such as self-knowledge, collaboration and problem solving. These skills are used daily in different life situations and are part of each person's process of learning to know, learning to live together, learning to work and learning to be, that is, they are part of everyone's integral training and development. In the 21st century, interconnectivity and the growing complexity of social, technological

transformations, among others, have increased the relevance of these skills for achievement in the personal, work and social spheres (OLIVEIRA, 2018, p.1).

From this perspective, the effectiveness in developing the aforementioned skills for the training of global leaders permeates the intellectual, emotional and social dimension, privileging the role played in a theoretical basis that refrigerates public policies in guaranteeing rights, constituting a transformative potential for concrete realities.

Educational spaces, from a Vygotskian perspective, enhance learning through sharing and exchanging experiences, where the effectiveness of leaders' actions permeates academic centers and the construction of education for all. Encouraging intellectual autonomy in students and the creation of proposals for the current world scenario, launches perspectives of future global leaders who will aim for actions that lead to the common good (LIMA; ALVES, 2022).

Experience shows us that leaders form leaders, as skills are empowered in a totally entrepreneurial vision, enhancing the innate skills of each individual, recognizing them as unique. According to Winck *et. al.* (2016), global leaders are able to influence people from different parts of the world and different cultures, motivating them to work together to achieve common goals.

The role of the leader and his leadership style are the factors that provoke changes, skills and stimuli to develop and influence the team, adding goals that, when shared, become a mutual responsibility between leader and followers, thus obtaining commitment, trust and quality of organizational microbehaviors in order to identify parameters of leadership skills in achieving established goals (PORTO *et. al.* , 2014, p. 2)

In this way, it is clear that the mission of educational centers in citizen training goes beyond the transmission of knowledge, but also involves socio-emotional aspects that enable children and young people to undertake goals and dreams that culminate in a new understanding of the world around them . return. It outlines the role of education in promoting transformative learning with the formation of critical citizens who begin to act socially, where Training processes prioritize skills that result in effective social integration.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

During this research, we realized the importance of the PDT's role in citizenship training and the development of global skills. In this regard, the formation of global leaders permeates the school space as it contributes to empowerment, stimulating student protagonism, intellectual autonomy and the ability to relate to oneself and others in a need to understand and understand

the world around you. In this way, the educator becomes a trainer of global citizens by developing in students values, skills, knowledge and attitudes in accordance with the global competencies necessary to build a more equal, inclusive and peaceful world.

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